

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Hernández Vargas et al.

**Guidelines for a database of
reclaimed precast concrete
elements**

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Abstract

The ReCreate project explores the possibilities of deconstructing and reusing precast concrete elements from end-of-life buildings that were not originally designed for disassembly. This report outlines a database for capturing, modelling, and exchanging data about reclaimed precast concrete. It focuses on database structuring, element verification, and the generation of standardised digital outputs for practical reuse in architecture and engineering.

Reusing precast concrete at scale requires that elements become available with sufficient documentation to architects and engineers. This report proposes a practical approach to achieving this by combining archival work, field documentation, and digital modelling into a coherent pipeline that produces an operational database structure. A prototype database demonstrated how each reclaimed element is documented as digital records linked to its donor building, including provenance, condition, material properties, and geometry, all expressed in a consistent format. The proposed workflow defines what is minimally needed to take an element from deconstruction to design, including naming conventions, traceable identifiers and interoperable exchange models.

Early implementations of the database on ReCreate's pilots suggest that heterogeneous stocks of elements can be organised and reintroduced into design with modest friction, provided that uncertainties (such as missing values or approximate measurements) are explicitly flagged and data exchange protocols are observed. The report outlines limitations, such as incomplete drawings and manual metadata curation, and proposes pragmatic extensions to the current methodology, including batch exports, API access, and closer ties to digital twins and material passports. The approach appears transferable to other contexts and provides a foundation for procurement and stock estimation based on real, reusable components. The database is complemented by an IFC workflow allowing elements to be exported into common project environments and BIM platforms.

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List of abbreviations

AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CC	Consequence Class
CE	Circular Economy
CDE	Common Data Environment
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
CSG	Constructive Solid Geometry
DDL	Data Definition Language
DT	Digital Twin
EER	Enhanced Entity–Relationship
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
ETL	Extract–Transform–Load
GIS	Geographic Information System
HCS	Hollow–Core Slabs
HRV	Heat Recovery Ventilation
ID	Identifier
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PK	Primary Key
PoC	Proof of Concept
QA	Quality Assurance
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
SQL	Structured Query Language
SRID	Spatial Reference System Identifier
UML	Unified Modelling Language
WKT	Well–Known Text
WKB	Well–Known Binary

1. Introduction

This report describes the conceptualisation and implementation of a reclaimed element database that records each element as an instance with persistent identifiers, geometry, reinforcement, materials, condition, and provenance. It formalises how these data are captured, validated, and made available in conventional workflows so that designers can select and reuse elements.

The construction sector accounts for a significant share of greenhouse gas emissions while also contributing to other types of environmental burdens, including the depletion of natural resources, high levels of energy consumption, and substantial waste generation (Bertin et al., 2022). Among strategies that reduce all these aspects, the reuse of building components from existing stocks offers one of the few viable ways to decouple construction from extraction. Yet, for reuse to scale beyond isolated case studies, it requires infrastructure that makes components searchable, their properties verifiable, and their exchangeable across projects.

The aim, then, should be to prioritise the reuse and recycling of materials already embedded within the existing building stock. This approach is framed within the concept of *Urban Mining*, a strategy situated in the broader discourse of the circular economy (CE). Urban Mining advocates the systematic recovery and reuse of anthropogenic materials sourced from urban environments, positioning the built environment itself as a reservoir of valuable resources (Honic et al., 2021). Precast concrete, manufactured at scale since the mid-twentieth century, constitutes a considerable inventory of standardised slabs, walls, beams and columns that are now entering phases of renovation or demolition.

Although precast concrete elements were not originally intended for circularity, their modularity offers an underexplored stock of durable, standardised components. While their reuse has long been technically feasible, *inter alia*, a lack of structured documentation and classification has hindered its widespread implementation. This report addresses that gap by presenting a comprehensive digital infrastructure for reclaimed precast elements. The database system serves as a base for storing precast element information, making it available for reuse in future projects. The current report documents the development of a relational database that supports classification, querying, and modelling of reused components; the spatial representation of geometric and reinforcement data; standardisation of element IDs; and the integration of this database into digital design environments.

Integrating reclaimed elements into current practices within the AEC industry requires that the database contents be accessible in the current workflows being used. This is done in two parallel and complementary approaches. *ReCreate Studio* is a prototype plug-in for Autodesk Revit that enables the management and import of database contents into the software's graphical user interface, minimising disruption to current practices. The second

approach is an experimental Python library, *ReCreate_IFC_workflow*, that generates native Industrial Foundation Classes (IFC) files from validated database entries. Built on the open-source library *ifcOpenShell* (*ifcOpenShell*, 2025), this pipeline preserves geometry and metadata without data loss in vendor-agnostic workflows supporting long-term interoperability.

This report is built on previous tasks within the ReCreate project. A digital map (Stenberg et al., 2025) comprised archival research, field documentation, and modelling routines on the geographic and typological distribution of precast concrete systems in eleven European countries. It established a repository of country dossiers, which provided a basis for historical documentation on precast concrete systems. An analysis of the typologies (Hernández Vargas & Stenberg, 2024) proposed a framework to describe precast concrete elements across three scales: buildings, components, and connectors. A taxonomic system (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025) introduced a faceted classification system and a naming convention that support the digital encoding of taxonomic knowledge about precast concrete elements and systems. The current report integrates these efforts into the conceptualisation and implementation of a database of donor precast concrete elements. The elements in this initial version are taken from four donor projects in the four leading countries in the project, and can be accessed here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16809738>.

The complete source code, developed in Python and SQL for the database presented in this research, has been released as open-source and distributed under the GNU General Public Licence v3.0, and is available at:

<https://github.com/bma114/ReCreate-Element-Database>.

Similarly, the Python library for the creation and manipulation of IFC files based on *ifcOpenShell* is released and publicly accessible through the following repository:

https://github.com/josehernandezvargas/ReCreate_IFC_workflow.

ReCreate Studio is thoroughly described in Fred Mudge's EngD thesis (Mudge, 2024). Finally, a scientific version of this work is being prepared as a journal article, which will provide a more in-depth coverage of the database's architecture and implementation.

The report is organised into four main sections. Chapter 2 presents the methodology, including the conceptualisation of the database, an overview of the workflow, and relevant standards. Chapter 3 describes the guidelines for data collection. Chapter 4 describes the implementation of data storage in MySQL. Chapter 5 explains BIM workflows to use the database of reclaimed elements in new projects. Finally, Chapter 6 summarises the discussion and gives concluding remarks.

2. Approach and database architecture

Architectural and structural design for reuse projects presents a distinct set of challenges when compared to conventional design development. Unlike new construction, where material properties and dimensions can be specified and adjusted, reuse scenarios involve working with pre-existing elements whose properties may be uncertain or partially undocumented (see Räsänen *et al.*, 2025). Further challenges include variability between available elements, dissimilar material properties, incomplete technical specifications, or undocumented interventions (*ibid.*). Designers working under these conditions require reliable identification mechanisms, access to source documentation, and a clear record of any deviations. Furthermore, all this information must be encoded in formats that allow interoperability across digital design tools and project phases.

The database plays a pivotal role in linking individual components to broader digital workflows, including digital twins and material passports. Since precast concrete elements are industrially manufactured and generally produced within system-specific constraints, their reuse depends on preserving that systemic logic. The classification used here reflects that understanding. The current chapter describes the conceptualisation and structure of the database. The section also documents the standards and conventions adopted for collecting, modelling, and managing data.

2.1. Key concepts

This section outlines the key concepts that support the approach: an element database serving as the authoritative source of record; digital twins that maintain an up-to-date representation of each physical element over time; and **material passports** that provide a structured dossier of composition, provenance, and reuse potential. The three are complementary. The database supplies strongly typed data, i.e., every record is restricted to a specific data type. Since the information is stored in a structured way, it can be searched and combined systematically, making the facts held in the database reliably queryable. The digital twin organises those facts as a time-aware asset model, while the passports enable traceability for downstream actors (designers, contractors, regulators) who need to verify suitability for reuse.

Precast concrete elements are standardised products that, in most cases, are part of a system. Therefore, at the core of the database is the distinction between an element class and building element instances. An element class refers to a 'blank element', i.e. the set of specifications of an element type, without any reference to any physical counterpart. In contrast, a 'donor building element' represents a particular instance of that class in a specific context, referring to a unique, physical entity. Each donor building element includes a persistent identifier, survey-based measurements, and metadata about the elements'

physical condition and history. These elements are the actual entities that can be reused, modelled, and assessed, while their relationship to the generic element definition (blank element) enables semantic structuring and grouping. Thus, the database functions as a centralised system for linking these abstract class definitions with their materialised counterparts. Attributes such as survey data, test results, production year, or quality control information are attached at the instance level, creating a traceable and well-structured record of each reused element.

2.2. Standards and conventions

The development of the database follows established standards to ensure consistency and interoperability. Construction classification draws on ISO 12006-2 for construction classification (ISO, 2020). BIM standards are based on ISO 19650 for building information management (ISO, 2019a), together with EN ISO 16739-1:2024 (ISO, 2024) which defines the IFC 4.3 schema, and ISO 10303-21:2016 specifies the STEP file format for model storage. Further guidelines for BIM-aided pre-deconstruction audits can be found in (Vullings et al., 2022) and (Vullings et al., 2024). Material properties and quality management also build upon previous reports within the ReCreate project (Räsänen et al., 2024, 2025). Similarly, names and IDs adhere to the faceted taxonomy previously developed within ReCreate (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025), including standardised codes for country, system, element type, manufacturer, and year.

Geometric properties follow the conventions specified in the tables in Section 3, with Cartesian coordinates in millimetres and reinforcement defined in terms of zones and planar profiles. All geometric definitions and internal voids are encoded as Well-Known Text (WKT) geometries in local coordinates (ISO, 2016b) to keep the core store compact and to simplify export rules. Structural checks are based on the Eurocode EN 1992 (CEN, 2008) specifying design rules for reinforced and prestressed concrete. Concrete performance is based on EN 206:2013+A2:2021 (SIS, 2024), which sets out durability requirements and exposure classes for concrete.

2.3. Data model

The data model follows an object-oriented approach to the problem. The database is structured to represent physical components (walls, slabs, beams, and columns) with properties and well-constrained relations, ensuring that meaning is preserved as data move from surveys and drawings into modelling and analysis. Implementation is relational. Relationships between tables are expressed as links between keys. Every table is assigned a primary key (PK), typically an auto-incrementing integer or structured identifier, while foreign keys (FKs) express relationships between records and maintain referential integrity. Candidate keys are used where natural uniqueness exists, such as internal designations (unique names or codes to identify components in that specific project) or donor-based IDs (labels derived from the donor building that ensure traceability), without replacing the system-assigned PKs. Human-readable identifiers, developed from the faceted

taxonomy (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025), are stored alongside technical keys to support both human legibility and automated traceability (see Section 3.2).

Universal Modelling Language (UML) is a language-agnostic, object-oriented visual modelling language for conceptualising the structure and relationships of complex systems. In the context of database design, UML diagrams are used to describe the logical schema of the database, with each class corresponding to a table, and attributes representing typed fields. These diagrams serve as a conceptual scaffold, helping teams from different backgrounds converge around a shared understanding of the data model before any implementation takes place. The UML model is then translated into an Enhanced Entity–Relationship (EER) schema, which introduces database-specific features such as cardinality constraints, inheritance, and composition. These constructs help clarify how elements relate to one another, for example, how SLAB, WALL, BEAM, and COLUMN inherit from a generic ELEMENT table, or how voids and reinforcement zones are compositionally tied to specific instances.

The distinction between identifying and non-identifying relationships is encoded structurally to distinguish dependencies from looser associations. For example, voids illustrate an identifying relationship, as they cannot exist without a parent element, and their identity is not separable from that element’s key. Conversely, the relationship between the element and the donor building is non-identifying, as it retains its own identifier independently. EER diagrams also allow for the explicit definition of cardinality constraints, which determine the maximum number of instances of one entity that may relate to another. For example, a one-to-one relationship can be observed, where each element instance is linked to a unique single identifier. A one-to-many relationship can be illustrated by the way a donor building may contain many elements. A many-to-many relationship can be exemplified by the association between elements and documents, since a single element may be linked to multiple drawings or reports, and each document can be associated with several elements.

Each class represent a table in the database, and the attributes in each class represent, in turn, table columns. Figure 1 shows the EER diagram for data collection, where each attribute is restricted to a specific data type (cf. Chapter 3), while the types of relationships are expressed with different symbols: inheritance (white arrow), composition (black arrow), and aggregation (black diamond). Inheritance expresses the transfer of attributes in a parent-child relationship, where the child item cannot exist without the parent. Composition declares relationships between a whole and its parts. Finally, Aggregation represents a looser association where entities can exist independently but still share a contextual link. Moreover, this data collection structure is primarily developed around parameterising an element’s geometry and reinforcement, including taxonomic information, material properties, metadata, and building data. It should be noted that other fields, such as findings of quality management or lifecycle analysis, which are included in the relational architecture, have not yet been integrated into the data collection process. The overall structure can be separated into groups of tables for each element type, i.e., walls, beams, slabs, and columns, which are represented by the dashed boxes.

Figure 1. UML class diagram of database structure for Data Collection phase. Note: the figure is a zoomable a vector graphic.

This level of detail is crucial for preserving semantic clarity and for enforcing relational integrity rules in implementation. By combining the abstract clarity of UML with the specificity of EER modelling and deploying these within a robust relational database management system (RDBMS), researchers can maintain standardised data structures, enable complex relational queries, and accommodate scalability as datasets expand into large datasets across multiple projects.

2.4. Proposed framework

The database is implemented in MySQL, an open-source RDBMS, and it is specifically designed to meet the requirements of concrete precast elements. The information model follows a top-down logic in which classes define standard semantics and instances capture the measurable properties, provenance and condition of a specific element. The architecture of the database is structured in three parallel schemas: i) the Core Schema stores normalised records with constraints and identifiers; ii) the Physical Properties Schema contains indexed and precomputed aggregates for frequent queries and exports; and iii) the Analysis Schema provides stable read-only views for search, reporting and downstream automation. Arrows indicate data flow across layers during ingestion and transformation, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Three-schema database architecture, including: i) Core Schema, ii) Physical Properties Schema, and iii) Analysis Schema, with their corresponding data flows.

The database workflow is organised into three consecutive stages, as shown in Figure 3. Currently, Stage 1 captures and structures evidence from drawings, surveys and tests; Stage 2 validates and stores the records within the relational schema with typed constraints and provenance; Stage 3 generates exchangeable models and embeds the data in BIM workflows.

Figure 3. The workflow for the database is divided into three discrete stages: 1.- Data Collection, 2.- Data Storage, and 3.- BIM Modelling.

Stage 1 comprises data collection, which is based on Microsoft Excel spreadsheet templates. At this stage, data is extracted manually from existing construction drawings or available test documentation (for more details, readers are referred to Räsänen et al., [2024], [2025]; and Vullings et al., [2022]). This manual approach was intentionally adopted during the pilot phase to develop a more nuanced and integrated understanding of the reuse process before transitioning to automation.

Stage 2 involves transferring this parametric data into a MySQL RDBMS. Once all data for a given donor building has been compiled, the spreadsheets are processed using Python scripts that convert the 2D coordinate information (Section 3.3) into standardised 3D geometries. This step includes aligning the collected data with mapping conventions and ensuring consistency for later modelling. The resulting outputs are machine-readable and structured to serve as inputs for future IFC-based digital modelling, bridging the gap between archival documentation and contemporary design tools.

Stage 3 focuses on generating BIM models and integrating workflows. Once records are validated and stored, element instances are transformed into exchangeable models. Export scripts map database fields to IFC 4.3 entities and property sets, generating files that preserve identifiers and provenance links. Geometry can be expressed as parametric volumetric shapes when appropriate, or as explicit coordinate-based profiles when greater fidelity is required. Reinforcement is represented through zoning and layering reference systems, which downstream tools may interpret as surrogate bar sets or as simplified proxies, depending on the level of detail available. The resulting models can be inspected and filtered through the ReCreate Studio interface (see Section 0) and can be imported by both commercial BIM platforms and open IFC-native tools. A lightweight screening routine

reads the stored geometry and reinforcement descriptors to provide indicative capacities for early design, with results kept clearly separate from formal verification. Feedback from design teams and site operations is then reintegrated into the element records, closing the loop between fieldwork, modelling and reuse decisions.

This workflow is explained in more detail in the upcoming chapters. Stage 1 is described in Chapter 3, while the storage (Stage 2) is discussed in Chapter 4, and the BIM modelling (Stage 3) is explained in Chapter 5.

3. Data collection

The data collection process is designed to produce a consistent and machine-readable record of each reclaimed precast concrete element. Source data includes original construction drawings, site measurements, scanned documents, deconstruction records, and metadata from donor buildings. For each entry, a minimum set of required fields is defined based on the classification scheme and database schema.

Figure 4. Data collection pipeline.

Structured Excel templates are used to collect data prior to import. These templates are aligned with the relational schema described in Figure 4 and facilitate manual entry of geometric parameters, reinforcement layout, and material properties. Each element is assigned a unique identifier based on the naming convention introduced in (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025), which encodes element type, country, manufacturer, system, year, and original designation (see Section 3.2 and Figure 5). Where available, historical classification systems are preserved in a separate metadata field, allowing for cross-referencing with archival documentation.

Geometry is recorded using Cartesian coordinates and local origin points, as defined in the data collection guidelines in Section 3. Elements are then partitioned into zones (by function and position), which then enables the reinforcement to be defined by two-dimensional layers (with constant spacing, diameter, and material). Each attribute in the database is accompanied by a required data type, which defines the specific format MySQL expects when storing the value. These data types are fixed. If a value is entered in an incorrect format, it triggers programmatic errors that prevent the data from being stored until the

format is corrected. The most common data types used during the collection process include the following:

- **Strings:** sequences of characters of variable length, typically used for names, codes, or descriptions.
- **Integers:** whole numbers used when fractional values are not expected or necessary.
- **Floats:** represent numbers that may include decimal points and are generally stored with a precision of up to seven decimal digits.
- **Boolean:** record binary values, typically expressed as TRUE or FALSE.
- **Vectors:** arrays containing two or more numeric values, often used to express spatial coordinates such as (x, y) or (x, y, z) .

The choice between using an integer or a float primarily depends on the precision required by the dataset. In many cases, floats are used when it is unclear whether a value may include decimal places. This approach avoids unnecessary errors while maintaining a flexible data model that accommodates diverse measurement conditions.

Data validation plays a central role in ensuring the reliability of the database. An important feature of EER diagrams is the clarification of Null vs. Not Null constraints. When building the database in MySQL, the schema requires a priori knowledge of whether an attribute can accept Null (empty or missing) inputs or whether it is mandatory to include a value (Not Null). This distinction is embedded within the database structure. Hence, during data collection, if the spreadsheet contains missing data that the RDBMS expects, loading errors will prevent the data from being uploaded. The tables in the following sections specify whether each attribute is optional or mandatory.

Data collection is managed through Microsoft Excel templates prepared in a format that reflects the information in Tables 1 to 13. The data is recorded manually for each element within a deconstruction project. Explanations of the required attributes are presented throughout Chapter 3. For guidance on the expected formatting of the data while moving through the process, refer to the data types specified in Section 3.3. To check whether a field is optional or mandatory, refer to the constraints outlined in the relevant table in Tables 1 to 13. Null means that the attribute is optional, and Not Null indicates that it is a mandatory parameter.

The following sections outline the inputs for each table based on the accompanying XLSX templates, the data structure, and the formatting required throughout the data collection stage. Flexible and robust Cartesian mapping conventions were adopted to capture any irregular or complex designs often seen in precast systems adaptively. Spatially capturing the geometrical and reinforcement properties will allow the elements to be more effectively remodelled and utilised to their full capabilities in new structural designs.

3.1. Donor building data

The donor building data can be found in the yellow tables in the top left corner of Figure 1. The *Donor Building* and *Circularity Data* tables only require a single record (row) for each deconstruction project. This data includes location, age, taxonomy, size, and circularity information. Any additional information that seems useful can be included in the *Notes* attribute. Table 1 below summarises the expected information for the *Donor Building* and *Circularity Data* tables.

Table 1. Donor Building Metadata attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Building ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	A multi-faceted taxonomy system of descriptive acronyms based on Hernández et al. (2025) and Stenberg et al. (2025). Figure 5 illustrates example taxonomies, where more information can be found in the resources mentioned above.
Name [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	e.g. 'Prinsenhof A' – ideally treated as a unique identifier.
Building Type [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	e.g., office building, industrial building, etc. – based on the donor building function.
Coordinates [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Latitude and longitude coordinates (not GPS).
Country [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The country where the building was constructed.
City [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	City where the building was constructed.
Construction Year [<i>year</i>]	Not Null	Numerical integer of the construction year.
Deconstruction Year [<i>year</i>]	Not Null	Numerical integer of the deconstruction year.
Deconstruction Company [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Name of the deconstruction company.
Consequence Class [<i>string</i>]	Null	CC based on Eurocode 1990-1:2023. Optional in case it is initially unknown – can be later updated.
Exposure Class [<i>string</i>]	Null	XC based on EN 206:2013+A2:2021. Optional in case it is initially unknown – can be later updated.
Total Floor Area [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Total deconstructed floor area, in m ² .

Number of Wings [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	If the donor building included sub-buildings. E.g. Prinsenhof had a high-rise, low-rise, and core component.
Number of Storeys [<i>list of integers</i>]	Not Null	Written as a vertical list of integers for each sub-building.
Number of Elements	Not Null	The number of elements by type that were deconstructed in sufficient condition for reuse. If they are not expected to be reused, do not count them here.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Any additional notes that might be useful to future designers (optional).

3.2. Element metadata

The metadata tables include a large amount of taxonomic information for each element. The [*Element ID*] attribute (e.g., Wall ID, Beam ID, etc.) is a facet-based classification system to serve as a unique, human-readable descriptor for each element (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025). Drawing upon research mapping pan-European precast concrete systems by Stenberg et al. (2025), the Building ID and element-type IDs encode the primary facets (project, manufacturer, year, location), substituting **UNK** placeholders for any unknown facets. Although these taxonomies are not replacements for formal national or international classification systems, they should be embedded into the Common Data Environment (CDE) for the given project (Dervishaj & Gudmundsson, 2025; ISO, 2019a). Figure 5 illustrates the general conventions with examples from the Swedish donor building. For more details on the different facets and acronyms, refer to Hernández Vargas et al. (2025). Table 2 summarises the expected information for the element metadata tables, with distinctions between any nuances related to the element type.

Figure 5. Building ID contains the taxonomic information from the precast system.

Table 2. Element Metadata attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Element ID [string]	Not Null	Wall ID, Beam ID, Column ID, or Slab ID based on Figure 5, b.
Building ID [string]	Not Null	Same as Table 1 and Figure 5, a.
Product ID [string]	Not Null	Unique ID specified in the original construction that identifies the unique product geometry. To avoid repetition across projects and ensure uniqueness, include the building project number as a prefix, e.g. 5415_HG01.
Reinforcement ID [string]	Null	Unique ID specified in the original construction that identifies a unique reinforcement design. Allows null in case drawings are not available. Include the project number as above. Wall: loading-bearing façade, internal wall, etc. Beam: rectangular, half-joint, T-beam, I-beam, etc. Column: rectangular, elliptical, headed, or I-section. Slab: hollow-core slab (HCS) or solid slab.
Element Type [string]	Not Null	Sub-building ID or name as described in Table 1.
Wing [string]	Not Null	Floor number where the element was in the donor wing.
Floor Number [int]	Not Null	Azimuth degrees format (0–359°). For standard mapping, N=0, E=90, S=180, and W=270 (<i>Only for wall elements</i>).
Orientation [int]	Not Null	Element position based on original construction drawings when available.
Grid Position [string]	Null	Does the element have any surface protection (e.g., plaster)?
Coating Layer [Boolean]	Null	“Active” for stored and available for reuse, “Pending” if under consideration for a new design, “Unavailable” if currently used in a new structure.
Status [string]	Not Null	Have any tests (material properties, degradation, durability, QA, etc.) been performed on the element?
Has Tests [Boolean]	Not Null	Does the element exhibit any damage that needs to be repaired or removed before being installation-ready?
Has Damage [Boolean]	Not Null	Class description of element condition (following QA): “Installation-Ready” , “Maintenance” , “Strengthening” .
Intervention Class	Not Null	Latitude and longitude coordinates of the storage location (not GPS).
Storage Lat/Long [string]	Not Null	

Notes [text]	Null	Any additional notes that might be useful to future designers (optional).
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3.3. Element geometry

For storage and interchange inside the database, geometric representations are encoded as Well-Known Text (WKT) geometries, following the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Simple Feature Access model (Open Geospatial Consortium, 2011). WKT is a text markup language used to describe vector-based geometric objects such as points, lines, polygons, and their compound forms, including 2D, 3D, and additional measures along a linear referencing system. Alongside WKT, a binary counterpart, Well-Known Binary (WKB), provides a more compact format that is generally preferred for efficient storage, although less human-interpretable. These notations are formalised in the broader ISO/IEC 132493:2016 standard, which defines how spatial data types and operations are implemented within SQL database systems (ISO, 2016b).

Figure 6. Examples of geometry definitions in well-known text (WKT) notation.

WKT supports a range of primitives, including POINT, LINESTRING, POLYGON, MULTIPOLYGON, and even complex types such as TIN (Triangulated Irregular Network) and GeometryCollection. It can express 2D, 3D (with "Z"), measured geometries (with "M"), or both (with "ZM").

In practice, element perimeters are stored as POLYGON Z in the element's local coordinate system, with inner rings representing voids (e.g., openings, recesses), and linear features (edges, cut lines) as LINESTRING Z. MySQL 8.x natively accepts these WKT types and enforces the topological closure requirement for polygons; ring orientation is normalised internally, so both clockwise and counterclockwise inputs are acceptable. Volumetric encodings, such as POLYHEDRALSURFACE or TIN, are avoided in the core store because they are not part of MySQL's supported set. Thickness and other extruded attributes are recorded explicitly as alphanumeric fields, which also keeps IFC export mappings straightforward.

Coordinates are recorded in a right-handed local system where x denotes length, z height, and y thickness. To remain compatible with WKT's $(x, y, [z])$ ordering, profiles are encoded as (x, z, y) when using Z ordinates; units are millimetres throughout. Polygon rings are closed by repeating the first vertex as the last; degenerate segments are disallowed by validation. When global geolocation is needed (e.g., for GIS queries), a separate centroid or placement is stored as a POINT with an EPSG SRID (typically 4326) and, where appropriate, the project's engineering CRS is described using WKTCRS as per ISO 19162, allowing unambiguous axis and unit declarations and transformations (ISO, 2019b).

Figure 7. Geometric definitions for different cross-sections: a) elliptical, b) rectangular, c) including corner radius. Although these conventions are specified generically for all element types, the elliptical cross-section is only used in columns.

The Cartesian coordinate system used to define the geometry of an element without being constrained to generic physical descriptors is illustrated in Figure 7. Following a traditional orthographic layout (elevation, cross-section, and plan view), the idea is to record the 2D coordinate position of every critical junction or discontinuity along the perimeter of the element. Standard CAD/BIM axis conventions are used for each view, shown in Figure 8, where x describes the global length, z is the global height, and y is the global thickness. Voids geometries are considered in a sub-table, so only the parent element geometry needs to be mapped for this stage. In brief, the process for recording the wall geometry is:

1. Using Western mathematical convention (**left to right, bottom to top**), identify the origin point $(0, 0)$ in each orthographic view.
2. After identifying the origin, **move clockwise** around the perimeter of each view, recording the coordinates at each junction. If ever in doubt whether a point is necessary, think whether the overall geometry could be digitally remade if it was missing, and otherwise include it.
3. An optional radius/bevel component is included with every point to describe any junctions or corners containing curvature or small tapered edges. If no curve or bevel is present, insert $r = 0$.
4. List each new coordinate point vertically in the spreadsheet to create a list. The coordinates can either be stored as integers or floats, depending on the level of accuracy available. Measurements are always recorded in mm.
5. Repeat for the next unique wall geometry.

Figure 8. Encoding example showing the relationship between the coordinate encoding using WKT, their meaning in orthogonal views, and the resulting 3D model.

3.3.1. Walls

Data collection from reclaimed wall elements includes façade elements and internal walls. These elements follow the standard mapping conventions described previously in Section 3.3. Since walls generally have the most complex geometries and reinforcement designs, load-bearing façades from the Prinsenhof donor building are used for visual examples. Figure 9 represents a typical façade geometry used in Prinsenhof (Product ID: 5415_G01).

Every unique wall geometry from a deconstruction project will have its geometry mapped and recorded here. There is no need to repeat this process for every element; only those with unique geometries that can be linked to the Wall Element table by the Product ID attribute (PK). The geometry considered in this table is for the load-bearing component only. If the additional outer sandwich layers, including the insulation layer, are kept for future designs, these geometries are stored in a connecting sub-table (see Table 5). Table 3 summarises the expected information for the 'Wall Geometry' table.

Figure 9. Geometric definition of the facade element G01 from the Prinsenhof A donor building in the Dutch pilot project. Please note that some details may differ from the actual element for representation purposes.

Table 3. Wall Geometry attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 2.
Reinforcement ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 2.
Mirrored Design? [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	A precast wall with identical geometry may be reflected about an axis to fit in a different position in the donor building – e.g. a corner or boundary element.
Count [<i>integer</i>]	Not Null	Number of elements sharing this geometry [Product ID], which are defined in Table 2.
Front View Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, z, r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Side View Coordinates [<i>list of points (y, z, r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Plan View Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, y, r)</i>]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Sandwich Panels [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	A Boolean indicating whether any additional (non-structural) panels are left attached to the load-bearing component.
Concrete Strength Class [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Concrete class based on original design specifications.
Max Aggregate Size [<i>int</i>]	Null	Maximum aggregate used in concrete mixture (optional).
Concrete Type [<i>string</i>]	Null	Type of concrete mix to determine density. Options may include: “Normal” , “Lightweight” , “Insulating ultralight” , “UHPC” , “Heavyweight” , “Pervious” .

Wall voids

The number of voids in a wall element typically determines the reinforcement design and specific reference system used to map the reinforcement. In a general sense, voids are defined as any recess bounded by at least three sides within the governing geometry. Hence, windows and doors are considered voids, whereas overhangs/cantilevers are deemed part of the overall geometry (similar for corbels, but these are treated as separate entities). Voids are linked to the global geometry through the *Product ID* attribute, which functions as a primary and foreign key.

The 3D coordinates (x, z, y) are recorded for every void corner throughout the thickness of the element. Any non-uniformity through the parent thickness or pitching is captured within the list of coordinates. The terminology for the different areas of a wall element is described in Section 3.3.1. Each point is vertically listed in the spreadsheet, similar to the geometry coordinates in Section 3.3. If there are no voids in the wall system, record a zero under the *Void Count* attribute and leave the other attributes empty – this will supersede the Not Null constraints for the other attributes. Table 4 summarises the expected information for the *Wall Voids* table.

Table 4. Wall Voids table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Void Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	The number of voids within a geometry.
Void Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, z, y)</i>]	Not Null	The 3D coordinates at each corner or geometric change are written as a vertical list.

Additional panelling

If any of the original sandwich panels are kept intact with the load-bearing component for use in future designs, the geometry can be mapped in this sub-table. These may include outer façade panels, exterior design finishes, insulation layers, or any other layer that does not contribute to the structural resistance of the principal wall element.

Table 5 treats the mapping for insulation layers and other panel types separately. This arrangement allows for slightly more freedom when mapping panels with irregular geometries, such as outer cladding, aesthetic layers or exterior architectural panels, while maintaining simplicity with insulation. Similar to Table 3, an optional radius or bevel component can be added to each coordinate point to describe curved, rounded, or tapered edges. If none are present, insert zero or leave blank. The external finishing and design parameters in Table 5 are currently optional placeholders which will be explored in more detail in future versions.

Table 5. Additional Panelling table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 2.
Has Void [<i>Boolean</i>]	Not Null	A Boolean for whether the panels have voids or not.
Panel Front Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, z, r)</i>]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same origin point as Table 3.
Panel Side Coordinates [<i>list of points (y, z, r)</i>]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same origin point as Table 3.
Panel Plan Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, y, r)</i>]	Null	Lists of coordinates as described in Section 3.3.1, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes. Use the same reference origin point as Table 3.
Panel Design Finish [<i>string</i>]	Null	An optional aesthetic description of the panel finish, which may include terms such as smooth, textured, rough, etc.

Insul. Front Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, z)</i>]	Null	List of coordinates for the front view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.
Insul. Side Coordinates [<i>list of points (y, z)</i>]	Null	List of coordinates for the side view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.
Insul. Plan Coordinates [<i>list of points (x, y)</i>]	Null	List of coordinates for the plan view of the insulation layer. Use the same reference origin as Table 3.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

When mapping the coordinates of extra panels, it is crucial to use the same local origin as defined in the primary geometry. Coordinates are recorded as lists following the same convention as Table 3 and outlined in Section 3.3. To simplify the data collection, no reinforcement is considered in these layers, only the geometrical properties.

Wall connections

The *Wall Connections* table describes any internal connections within the wall geometry that were recovered or can be recovered post-deconstruction. For example, in element *G01* in Figure 9, two M20 (20 mm diameter) bolt connections are fixed into the upper boundary with an approximate depth of 165 mm. The connections extended above and inserted into voids in the underside of the next wall. The voids were then backfilled with grout or mortar to create the wall-to-wall connection during assembly. Theoretically, even once the connection is cut along the wall boundary during deconstruction, the ungrouted rod component can be removed without damaging the inlaid thread, making the connection reusable. It is assumed that the grout-filled voids will not be cored out after deconstruction; however, this is also possible. Therefore, it is helpful to include any existing connections that can be recovered to serve future designs. Another typical example is wall-to-wall starter bars, which follow the same premise as the bolted connections, where the upper component can be removed after deconstruction (illustrated in Annex A, Figure A1).

Each record in the spreadsheet describes a single connection (no lists) and includes the 3D point location, depth, diameter, and a type description (e.g. bolted, starter bar, etc.). If the diameter of a bar or bolted connection is given as a string (e.g. M20, M24, etc.), convert it into an integer or float when recording the data. If no recoverable connections exist, inserting a zero into the Count attribute will override the Not Null constraints for the other attributes, which can be left empty.

Table 6 summarises the expected information for the Wall Connections table.

Table 6. Wall Connections table attribute and descriptions

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Integer counting the number of recoverable connections.

Location Coordinates [<i>point</i> (x, z, y)]	Not Null	3D point location of each recoverable connection. E.g., G01 has two connections: (200, 3480, 90) and (3384, 3480, 90).
Depth [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Connection depth in mm. Integer or float.
Diameter [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Diameter in mm. Integer or float.
Connection Type [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Description of connection. Recorded in uppercase letters, e.g., BOLTED or STARTER BAR.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

Corbel geometry

Corbels are treated separately from the primary geometry to simplify the shape and reinforcement modelling. The method for mapping corbel geometries is approached generically to improve efficiency within the database. A single table is dedicated to storing corbel information from walls, beams, and columns, which can be found in the central area of Figure 1.

The mapping convention follows the same method as outlined in Section 3.3.1. However, since a corbel typically only occupies two planes, one view can be omitted for simplicity. The remaining plane is recorded in the *Extruded Plane* column (“XZ”, “YZ”, or “XY”), for downstream automated extrusion. For example, all necessary points can be captured from the side and plan views in Figure 9, so the front view (XZ) can be left empty.

The proposed methodology also flexibly captures recesses and discontinuities in the corbel geometry. For example, element G01 has two 100 mm tapered recesses along its span (Figure 9). These are essential aspects to capture parametrically, as they influence the reinforcement design, development lengths, and support lengths for seated floor slabs. The orange markers in Figure 9 illustrate the coordinates to be recorded. Table 7 summarises the expected information for the *Corbel Geometry* table.

Table 7. Corbel Geometry table attributes and description.

Attribute [<i>data type</i>]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 2.
Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	An integer for the number of corbels in a given Product ID.
Extruded Plane [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The remaining plane is not parametrically described by the coordinates below. Choose from either XZ , YZ , or XY .
Front View Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, z, r)]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the front elevation of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Side View Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (y, z, r)]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the cross-sectional view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.
Plan View Coordinates [<i>list of points</i> (x, y, r)]	Not Null	Coordinate system as described above, based on the plan view of the orthographic drawing and relevant axes.

Notes [text]	Null	Additional technical notes might be helpful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.
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3.3.2. Slabs

Slabs are divided into two main categories: solid and hollow-core slabs. Solid slabs present a straightforward geometric definition, which simplifies the identification of reinforcement and the arrangement of layers, while still accommodating the complexities introduced by inlaid voids for essential building services. On the other hand, hollow-core slabs represent a standardised solution in modern construction, with their geometry and structural properties readily described by a concise set of physical attributes.

Solid slabs

Solid floor slabs follow the same conventions as walls described in Section 3.3. Slab geometry is much simpler than that of walls, making the definitions of geometrical zones and reinforcement layers easier as well. The only noteworthy distinction here is that, unlike beams and columns, voids are again considered due to the possibility of inlaid voids for ducting, plumbing, and other installations. Otherwise, the approach for mapping the geometry, longitudinal reinforcement design, and transverse reinforcement design is described in Sections 3.3.1, 3.3.2, and 3.3.3.

Hollow-core slabs (HCS)

Prestressed hollow-core floors are a highly standardised slab design that can be parameterised in a more straightforward format than was necessary for the earlier element types. The general geometric and void properties, connections, structural topping details, and prestressing information are outlined in the following sections.

HCS geometry

The geometry of an HCS can be directly characterised by physical dimensions instead of a spatial system. Table 8 summarises the attributes required to describe a hollow-core slab. Figure 10. Typical hollow-core slab section from Prinsenhof A office complex. Figure 10 provides a visual aid for deriving the required properties.

Figure 10. Typical hollow-core slab section from Prinsenhof A office complex.

Table 8. HCS Geometry table attribute and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Product ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Product ID matching Table 2.
Reinf ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 2.
Count [<i>integer</i>]	Not Null	Number of elements with identical geometry [Product ID].
Height [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Cross-sectional height, in mm.
Length [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Floor slab length, in mm.
Width [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Cross-sectional width, in mm.
Void Count [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Number of cores in the slab.
Void Diameter [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Core diameter in the horizontal and vertical directions (see Figure 10).
Concrete Cover [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Concrete cover depth to the bottom and top of the cores, in mm.
External Web Thickness [<i>float</i>]	Not Null	Thickness of the outer web between the slab edge and outer core, in mm.
Concrete Strength Class [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Concrete class based on original design specifications.
Density [<i>float</i>]	Null	Known or approximated concrete density in kg/m ³ .
Max Aggregate Size [<i>int</i>]	Null	Maximum aggregate used in concrete mixture (optional).
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

HCS Connections

The connections considered in HCS floor systems include:

- Shear connections between slabs and walls (located along the outer edge) and their position in mm.
- Longitudinal connections between slabs and walls (located at slab ends) and their position in mm.
- Shear connections between adjacent slabs (located along the inner edge) and their position in mm.

When a floor system is deconstructed, the connections between adjacent elements are sawn through. If the connections are left in the slab, designers must be aware that this area is compromised and cannot be used for future connections. Likewise, if the connection is removed, the void left in its place will likely be backfilled and cannot be used in future connections. For simplification, only the function and position of the connection are recorded. Designers can refer to the original drawings for specific details. If no connections are present, enter 0 in the data field.

Structural topping

For reuse purposes, knowledge about whether the structural topping layer is still attached to the slab is also necessary. Since the topping will have been sawn down the longitudinal edge of the slab during deconstruction, the diaphragm action it supplied can no longer be achieved. However, it is often left in place due to the significant difficulty of effectively removing the topping without damaging the slab. The topping will affect both structural and architectural design phases for reuse, so it needs to be accounted for in the database. Table 9 summarises the attributes required for the structural topping.

Table 9. Structural Topping table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Present? [Boolean]	Not Null	True or False Boolean identifying if a structural topping is still in place.
Thickness [int]	Not Null	Thickness of structural topping, in mm.
Mesh Diameter [int]	Null	Diameter of the steel mesh reinforcement inside the slab, in mm (optional).
Mesh Spacing [int]	Null	Grid spacing (assumed uniform) of the steel mesh reinforcement inside the slab, in mm (optional).

HCS prestressing

Prestressing information in HCS systems is critical for determining the slab's load-bearing capacities. Table 10 summarises the attributes required for the prestressing design in hollow-core floor slabs. The *prestressing layer* describes all strands along the same horizontal x-axis position. The *Layer Number*, therefore, represents the relative position of the layer, starting at the base and incrementing vertically.

Table 10. HCS Prestressing table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [string]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 2.
Strand ID [string]	Not Null	Unique ID for each prestressing strand in an element. Serves as the primary key in the MySQL RDBMS.
Layer Number [int]	Not Null	The prestressing layer number, starting from the slab base.
Strand Coordinates [point (x,y)]	Not Null	The cross-sectional position of each prestressing strand.
Number of Wires [int]	Not Null	The number of wires used in each tendon, e.g. 1-wire, 3-wire, or 7-wire strand, etc.
Strand Diameter [float]	Not Null	Diameter of the prestressed tendon in mm.
Strand Grade	Null	Steel grade designation for the prestressed tendon.
Notes [text]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be of use to future designers.

3.3.3. Columns

Data collection for column elements follows the same general principles and methodologies discussed in Section 3.3. Like beams, the process begins with mapping the geometry, longitudinal reinforcement design, and transverse reinforcement design. The primary differences between the walls and columns are:

- The *Void* table has been removed.
- The *Additional Panelling* table has been removed.
- Elliptical and curved cross-sections are considered.

Two primary cross-sectional types can be defined for columns: *elliptical* and *rectangular* cross-sections. An ellipse is described entirely by tangential coordinates. A tangent line is drawn between two infinitely close points on a plane curve, resembling a line parallel to the curved surface. Hence, a tangent line cannot be drawn relative to a straight edge, where the distance between two parallel points is no longer infinitesimally small. If the intersection of the tangents from four points of contraflexure along a curved surface creates a bounding rectangle, then the section is considered elliptical. If a curved section includes straight portions, then it is regarded as a rectangular section with curved edges. Circular sections are elliptical sections with a constant diameter. Similarly, square sections are rectangular sections of constant width. For the *Cross-Section* attribute in the *Column Geometry* table, record either **elliptical** or **rectangular**.

3.3.4. Beams

The data collection of beam elements conceptually follows the same mapping conventions and reference systems as the wall elements discussed throughout Section 3.3. In general, the process for collecting beam data involves:

1. Mapping the geometry in a 2D orthographic format.
2. Mapping the longitudinal steel design by defining the zone and layer reference systems.
3. Mapping the transverse reinforcement design by defining the shape of the bars within each zone.

By implementing zones, irregular cross-sections can be partitioned and simplified, enabling the reinforcement design to be more easily defined. The attributes used to describe steps 1 to 3 above are the same as those used for walls. The only distinguishing differences are:

- The *Void* table has been removed.
- The *Additional Panelling* table has been removed.
- The *zone naming convention* has changed. For beams, zones are designated as either **flange (F)** zones, **web (W)** zones, or a **single zone (Z)** for uniform sections.

Figure 11. Zone allocation for different beam types.

Figure 11 provides examples of beam elements and their possible zoning, along with the new naming convention. Remember that as long as the rules outlined in Section 3.3.2 are followed, the selected zones can vary based on the user’s preference. However, half-joints in beams are classified as part of the global geometry, not corbels, so the data should be structured accordingly.

3.4. Reinforcement

Spatially defining the reinforcement design is critical for assessing the role of an element in new structural designs. Without understanding the unique reinforcement design in each element, structural analyses cannot be performed, and the only reuse function a reclaimed element may serve is in a downcycled capacity (i.e. the demands in the new structure are less than in the original donor structure). Parameterising the longitudinal reinforcement design poses several challenges, particularly in wall elements. First, the frequency of voids and discontinuities increases the complexity of the design, while the designation of longitudinal and transverse axes varies with component function. To adaptively capture the reinforcement design in a robust manner that applies to systems with n number of voids, elements are partitioned into **zone** and **layer** reference systems.

A zone is defined as a continuous bounding polygon that extends from one discontinuity or void to the next. Each zone is described by a 2D polygon within its specified *Zone Plane* descriptor, corresponding to the primary cross-sectional view, assuming constant extrusion through the remaining plane. Wall zones can be classified as follows:

- **Base (B):** Horizontal wall zones beneath voids (sills).
- **Header (H):** Horizontal wall zones above voids (lintels).
- **Flank (F):** Vertical flanking zones beside voids (walls).
- **Single (Z):** Uniform geometry without voids or discontinuities.
- **Corbel (_C):** Dedicated zones for corbels, prefixed by primary zone (Fig. 3.4).

Hence, the number of zones within an element depends on the frequency and location of voids. Figure 12 represents a single-void system, whereas a standard double-void system typically includes a door and a window. Annexe A presents examples of geometries with different voids and zones. The sum of all zone areas should encompass the entire geometry of the element. Figure 12 illustrates the zone reference system for element G01.

Once the element geometry has been completely partitioned, reinforcement **layers** within each zone can be defined. A *layer* describes a set of reinforcing bars with constant diameter, spacing, and steel grade within the same plane. Zones and layers follow a few simple rules:

- Zones must encompass the entire length of each reinforcement layer within that zone, with no partial coverage.
- Layers must maintain uniform spacing, diameter, and grade, with any variation requiring a new layer.
- Layer positions are recorded as centre-to-centre measurements.

Therefore, the process of mapping the longitudinal reinforcement design can be summarised into the following steps, using Figure 12 and Figure 13 guides:

1. Identify all of the zones within an element and record the polygon coordinates (e.g., $((x_1, z_1), (x_2, z_2))$).
2. Identify the orientation and number of layers within each zone (see Figure 13).
3. In the first zone, select the first bar in the layer (closest to the origin or axis).
4. Define the start and end points of the bar, resembling a *linestring*.
5. Define the number of bars within the layer, the diameter of the bars, the spacing, and the steel grade.
6. Move on to the next layer within the zone and repeat.
7. Avoid recording duplicates of any layers or bars. Each layer or bar only needs to be recorded once.

When corbels are present, they are assigned their own zone and receive the necessary reinforcement layers. In Figure 13, although the 5 mm longitudinal rebars in the corbels are aligned with identical bars in zone *H1*, the spacing varies, so the corbel reinforcement is given its own layers *L1* and *L2* (within zone *H1C*). The zone ID assigned to a corbel zone should start with the same zone name as the overall section it is located in, suffixed by a 'C', followed by an incrementing integer (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Example zoning convention for Prinsenhof façade element G01.

Table 11 summarises the expected information for the Wall Long Reinforcement table. The concrete cover is separated into the (x, y, z) directions to account for situations of non-uniform cover around the section. Additionally, depending on the position of the reinforcement layer, the reported depth to the concrete surface may be associated with a different global axis, which can be specified using this format, while entering zero for the other axes. The construction confidence margin specified in the original drawings is also required. If a wall is mirrored in Table 3, there is no need to create a new record of the reinforcement design; the mirrored design can be linked to the original design via the *Reinf ID*.

There is a substantial amount of freedom when it comes to defining the zone and layer reference systems. So long as all steel reinforcement is accounted for within an element with the correct geometrical and spatial properties, then the specific details of how the zones are defined are less critical. Element KG03 illustrates an excellent example of this in Figure A1. Here, the wall has no voids, but due to the irregular profile in the y direction, the element could be subdivided into three zones – Flank 1 (F1), Flank 2 (F2), and Flank 3 (F3). The zones would be designated as flanks instead of base zones or headers because the primary load-bearing and bending reinforcement (*longitudinal reinforcement*) is oriented

vertically. This approach enables changes in reinforcement sizes and spacings to be captured across different areas throughout the section. However, the same result could be achieved by using only a single all-encompassing zone, with the necessary spatial information captured in the layer data, since all rebar vertically span the same length from bottom to top. As long as changes in diameter and spacing are captured by creating new layers where necessary, any specific approach using the proposed generic framework will achieve the same outcome. The proposed methods offer a degree of improvement to the efficiency of the process and downstream modelling applications.

Table 11. Wall Long Reinforcement table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 2.
Zone ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Name given to each zone. E.g. B1, F1, F2, H1, HC1 . "C" is given to zones representing corbels.
Zone Plane [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The plane that the polygon extends over. Either XZ, YZ, or XY .
Zone Start [<i>point</i> (h_1, v_1)]	Not Null	Starting zone coordinates (horizontal, vertical).
Zone End [<i>point</i> (h_2, v_2)]	Not Null	Ending zone coordinates (horizontal, vertical).
Layer ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Sequential labelling of each layer, written as L[x] (Fig. 3.5).
Concrete Cover [<i>point</i> (x, z, y)]	Null	Mean concrete cover depth in each direction, in mm.
Concrete Cover Confidence (\pm) [<i>int</i>]	Null	Construction confidence margin in cover depth specified in the original drawings (e.g. ± 5 mm).
Layer Start [<i>point</i> (h_1, v_1)]	Not Null	Starting layer position (horizontal, vertical). Taken at the centre of the bar.
Layer End [<i>point</i> (h_2, v_2)]	Not Null	Ending layer position (horizontal, vertical). Taken at the centre of the bar.
Layer Position [<i>point</i>]	Not Null	Centre position of the first bar in the layer relative to the plane not included in <i>Zone Plane</i> (closest to the axis or origin).
Number of Bars [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Number of bars in the layer.
Bar Diameter [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	The diameter of each bar in the layer, in mm.
Bar Spacing [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Centre-to-centre spacing between each bar in the layer (constant).
Steel Grade [<i>string</i>]		Specified steel grade reported in the original design documentation.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

The anchoring conditions at the end of each rebar and layer are critical for several capacity estimations involving bond development lengths and stress-strain relationships. Ordinarily, hooks of various lengths, shapes, and radii are applied to the rebar ends to anchor them within the concrete. Systems of this variety can be considered **layer anchorage** systems, as they provide anchorage on a per-bar (per-layer) basis. However, hairpin systems (U-shaped bars) are often used as an alternative means of anchoring the reinforcement cage over a **zone**, rather than each bar individually. Therefore, the ratio of hairpins to layers is not always 1:1 (Figure 13), creating discrepancies when recording the data. The data collection templates separate anchorage systems into either *layer* or *zone anchorage*. Table 12 summarises the attributes of both types of reinforcement anchorage.

Table 12. Steel Anchorage table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Anchorage Type [string]	Not Null	Description of anchorage type in capital letters. E.g. HOOKED (layer), HAIRPIN (zone), NONE.
Bent Angle (layer) [float]	Not Null	Record the start (left or bottom) and end (right or top) angle of any hook in degrees.
Hooked length (layer) [float]	Not Null	Record the length of a hook at the start (left or bottom) and end (right or top) of a bar. Enter zero if an end is straight.
Bent Angle (zone) [float]	Not Null	Each bent angle in the hairpin. This allows irregular shapes to be captured. Record each angle as a list.
Radius [float]	Not Null	The radius of a bend, if it has curvature, in mm. Enter zero if there is no radius.
Diameter [int]	Not Null	Diameter of hairpins, in mm.
Spacing [int]	Not Null	Spacing between pins as specified in drawings, in mm.
Number of Pins [int]	Not Null	Number of pins within the zone.
Pinned Span [string]	Not Null	The span over which the pins are spaced. Requires X , Y , or Z as input.
Notes [text]	Null	Any additional technical notes, e.g., if hairpins are only on one side or vary on either side of a zone.

If no end conditions are applied to a bar, leave it empty in the datasheets. In this case, there should be hairpins or some other system providing anchorage to the bars or group. However, in the context of this database, the anchorage attributes only consider the end conditions of each bar or group of bars, not the development lengths based on code guidelines. For this reason, a straight rebar with no hooked conditions (no layer anchoring) and no hairpins (no zone anchoring) can be inserted as **NONE** in the *Anchorage Type* attribute. For zone anchorage, record properties only once, in the row corresponding to the correct zone in the spreadsheet.

The transverse reinforcement design follows the longitudinal reference system developed earlier. Based on each zone, the shape of the transverse reinforcement is defined by recording a list of each critical point in the bent shape. This is achieved by specifying the 2D plane in which the reinforcement is bent (XZ, YZ, or XY), the angle at each point in the shape, and the coordinates corresponding to the necessary plane. Such an approach enables the recording of irregular geometries without the need for a shape code typically

found in manufacturing standards. This system assumes the transverse reinforcement is not bent in multiple directions and can be described in a 2D plane. If a stirrup has an open end or a transverse rebar has a straight end, enter 0 degrees into the bent angle.

A zone can have more than one entry as long as it is correctly identified, which may be necessary when two parallel straight or bent rebars are placed in the element instead of stirrups. Each rebar layer should be recorded separately to capture any niche details. An example case can be found in element KG03 from the Prinsenhof data and in Figure A1. Table 13 summarises the attributes required to map the transverse reinforcement design.

Table 13. Wall Transv Reinf table attributes and descriptions.

Attribute [data type]	Constraint	Description
Reinf ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Unique Reinforcement ID matching Table 2.
Zone ID [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The identifier given to each zone, matching Table 11.
Description [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Description of transverse reinforcement type, e.g., closed stirrup, open stirrup, bent rebar, straight rebar, etc.
Bar Diameter [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Diameter of transverse reinforcement, in mm.
Spacing [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Spacing of reinforcement within the zone, in mm.
Num. Bends [<i>int</i>]	Not Null	Number of bends in the reinforcement shape. This value should match the length of the <i>Shape</i> list next.
Bent Plane [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The plane over which the transverse reinforcement is bent (based on the orthographic drawing) – XZ , YZ , or XY .
Shape [<i>list of points</i> (θ, x, z, y)]	Not Null	A list of three points at each bend in the shape. Includes an angle, θ , and the coordinates matching the <i>Bent Plane</i> entered above – i.e. one axis will be left empty.
Span Axis [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The span over which the transverse reinforcement is spaced, i.e. whatever axis is not included in the <i>Bent Plane</i> – X , Y , or Z .
Span Position [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	The start and end points of the reinforced span.
Steel Grade [<i>string</i>]	Not Null	Specified steel grade reported in the original design documentation.
Notes [<i>text</i>]	Null	Additional technical notes that might be useful to designers, including any details missed by the attributes.

Figure 13. Reinforcement design in Prinsenhof element G01 in the Dutch pilot.

3.5. Material properties

The material specifications from historical national standards are stored in a collective library within the database. The database is structured so that only the concrete strength class or steel grades are required for input in Tables 3, 8, 10, 11, and 13. The class or grade specifications are then linked to the properties library via an FK relationship. Manufacturing standards from the 20th and 21st centuries have been collected and stored from each country, including the modern Eurocode provisions. Material properties from standards dating back to 1918 for reinforcing steel and 1918 for concrete have been collected from each ReCreate partner country. This work is ongoing, and to further build and improve the libraries, it would be beneficial for each country cluster to review its archives and incorporate information from its respective country codes into the libraries. The material libraries are publicly available at the following Zenodo repository:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16809569>.

4. Data storage

To record elements into the database, each component must be analytically deconstructed into a comprehensive set of parametric descriptors (see Chapter 3). These descriptors serve as the foundation for reconstructing accurate 3D digital models, enabling architects and engineers to incorporate reclaimed elements into new structural designs. To demonstrate and evaluate this approach, proof-of-concept (PoC) workflows have been developed, showing how digital modelling can effectively support element reuse.

The repository is organised into four, clearly scoped directories:

- **schemas/** holds DDL (Data Definition Language scripts) that create the database structure for the Core, Physical properties and Analysis schemas and seed data for reference tables. DDL refers to the SQL commands used to define or alter database objects such as tables, views, or indexes.
- **models/** contains the conceptual EER models (see Section 2.3) exported as editable diagrams, which mirror the DDL and help reviewers validate keys, relations and cardinalities.
- **configs/** provides YAML configuration files that declare field mappings between the XLSX templates and the Core schema and, separately, between the Core and the Physical properties or Analysis schemas.
- **source/** stores the Python codebase: the command-line loader, extract-transform-load (ETL) routines, WKT parsing utilities and other helper functions.

The repository targets Python 3.9 and MySQL 8.0 or superior. Installation consists of creating the three schemas, applying the DDL scripts in sequence and granting restricted roles for loaders and readers. Connection and runtime settings are provided through environment variables or a .env file, such as DB_URI, DB_USER, DB_PASSWORD, SRID_DEFAULT, LOG_LEVEL, and BATCH_SIZE. Configuration files in configs/ define the mapping from spreadsheet columns to database attributes, including unit conversions, controlled vocabularies and default values for optional fields. These mappings are explicit and versioned, ensuring that data imports remain reproducible even as templates evolve.

4.1. Donor element database

The current implementation includes entries from the donor buildings in all four ReCreate pilot countries: Sweden, Finland, the Netherlands, and Germany. These deconstructed buildings included apartment buildings, office complexes and an industrial warehouse. These real-life projects provided both practical insights and theoretical reflections on how to plan and execute deconstruction processes in real-world conditions (Vullings et al., 2024). Importantly, the reclaimed components encompassed all four precast element types in the database, each of which is now slated for reuse in forthcoming construction projects.

Figure 14. Donor buildings for each of the ReCreate pilot projects: a) Finland, b) Germany, c) Sweden, and d) the Netherlands.

Data was collected from technical drawings, deconstruction audits, and digital scans. Each entry includes geometric data, classification metadata, and reinforcement layout. The donor database is used to identify available elements for reuse in new projects and also serves as a test case for digital modelling routines and structural capacity estimation. Elements are linked to their building of origin and cross-referenced with system-level typologies to support traceability.

The current PoC workflow for data collection relies on XLSX templates, prepared individually for each precast element type. In its early stages, data was gathered manually, with information extracted directly from available construction drawings and test documentation. This manual approach was a deliberate choice during the conceptual phase, as it enabled a more thorough and contextual understanding of the reuse chain before pursuing automation. To support this process, the authors have prepared a comprehensive data collection guideline that outlines every relevant variable, including data types, formatting conventions, and validation constraints associated with the XLSX templates. The full documentation and template package are accessible via the project's public repository, offering a reproducible reference for future users.

4.2. Automated capacity estimation

The current database schema enables a multi-stage pipeline to perform automated structural capacity estimations in accordance with the Eurocode. The system transforms

the parametric and scalar information stored in the Core schema into physical properties, which are then fed into the Analysis schema to provide bending capacity estimations that can be applied to beams and slab elements. For this, the data collected from the Excel templates is imported as a relational MySQL schema, where the data is normalised. Then, the physical properties schema automatically calculates attributes from the core schema processing dimensions, volumes, masses, centroids and other measurable properties. These results are populated into a separate schema, keeping a distinction between manual records and derived metrics, while preserving provenance. YAML-based mapping files allow for standardised calculations.

The Analysis pass applies structural formulae to the combined Core and Physical properties data, populating a separate Analysis schema. The current implementation demonstrates automated flexural resistance checks for reinforced concrete beams, following Eurocode principles, and shows how resistance values can be embedded directly in the database for reuse assessments. The pipeline can be readily adapted to perform design calculations according to country-specific National Annexes. The function takes as input the concrete and steel strengths, reinforcement areas, effective depths, and partial factors, returning a design moment resistance. Although the current PoC only includes an implementation of the flexural capacity for beams, the framework is extensible to other checks, including shear, torsion, axial-bending interaction, and serviceability verifications. Importantly, this pass demonstrates the database's capacity to progress beyond descriptive cataloguing into the domain of automated performance estimation.

In practice, the pipeline relies on manual input during the collection and Core schema, particularly for donor building metadata, material specifications, and geometric and reinforcement data. By contrast, the automated calculations begin with the Physical properties pass and continue through to the Analysis pass, where reproducible and standardised methods are applied consistently across the dataset. Semi-automated configuration is implemented through YAML mappings, which link database fields to specific formulae; this allows practitioners to extend or customise the analysis without altering the underlying code.

In a real-world project setting, this framework should be understood as both a catalogue of reclaimed elements and a decision-support environment. At the catalogue level, it provides searchable, structured inventories enriched with physical descriptors such as weight, dimensions, and material classes. At the decision-support level, it enables preliminary feasibility checks in AEC environments. Architects might use the database to filter reclaimed slabs by depth, span, or mass, allowing them to sketch layouts that are grounded in what is available. Engineers, in turn, may query the computed bending capacities to verify whether a stock of beams can reasonably meet the requirements of a proposed reuse project. The catalogue thus functions as both inventory and filter, narrowing the design space to options that are physically and structurally realistic. It is important to note that the outputs are not intended to replace full-scale design verification, but rather to supply an automated and standardised baseline for preliminary assessment and decision-making.

Furthermore, the current database pipeline might, in a sense, function as a foundational digital shadow. It represents physical components in a digital form, derived from site-acquired data and transformed into analytical attributes via automation. Although this may not fulfil the full definition of a digital twin according to certain authors, who consider that a DT requires dynamic, real-time interaction between physical and digital systems (Kritzinger et al., 2018). However, the database system presented in this report does provide the groundwork for more advanced implementations.

5. BIM modelling

Open BIM, understood as the application of open standards and interoperable workflows across the design, construction, and operation of buildings, is grounded in the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standard, as specified in EN ISO 16739-1 (2024). IFC functions as a comprehensive and vendor-neutral data model that encodes both the geometry of a building and the full set of attributes associated with its components. Beyond the representation of individual objects, the schema preserves the relationships and dependencies that structure the building as a whole, enabling information to be exchanged across diverse software platforms without loss of meaning or integrity.

However, current industry practices are still dependent on proprietary software environments where the source code is not available. Therefore, the development of ReCreate Studio (Figure 15) targets Autodesk Revit, one of the major vendors of BIM solutions in the industry. This ensures the inclusion of reuse, minimising the friction with current practices. In parallel, the development of an experimental pipeline based on ifcOpenShell supports the open data standards required for the project.

Figure 15. Example of the interface of ReCreate Studio in Revit (Mudge, 2024).

5.1. ReCreate Studio

The integration of reused precast concrete components into the design of new buildings represents a shift in how structures are conceived and calculated. Since this approach lacks a long-standing tradition in the construction industry, it implies a demand for tools that can accommodate and streamline unfamiliar processes without forcing practitioners to abandon their existing ecosystems.

Rather than inventing entirely new platforms, the more pragmatic route is to embed circular logic into the digital environments architects and engineers already use. ReCreate Studio was developed as a prototype plug-in for Autodesk Revit, intended to bring the concept of element-by-element reuse into the realm of everyday design practice (Mudge, 2024). Written in C#, the add-in operates as a modular class library that connects the relational element database to Revit's graphical environment via its public API (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Automatic capacity estimations in ReCreate Studio (Mudge, 2024).

5.2. IFC modelling

The growing maturity of open-source tools for Building Information Modelling (BIM) has opened the door to implementing IFC-based workflows independently of proprietary software environments. While IFC is broadly recognised as the standard for data exchange, many day-to-day workflows still depend on native file formats tied to closed ecosystems. Nonetheless, a shift is underway: tools that treat IFC as a native modelling format are increasing in adoption both in practice and research. There, they enable experimental

modelling approaches, facilitate reproducible case studies, and support the integration of BIM with geospatial systems and heritage documentation, expanding the scope of what BIM can represent and preserve.

ReCreate_IFC_Workflow provides a modular pipeline for translating database entries into IFC files, ensuring compatibility with a wide range of workflows through an open and software-agnostic format. At the core of this implementation is *IfcOpenShell*, a flexible open-source library written in C++ with Python bindings, purpose-built to handle both high- and low-level operations on IFC data structures (*IfcOpenShell*, 2025). Its geometry processing routines are grounded in the ISO 10303-21 specification (ISO, 2016a), which defines the syntax and file structure of STEP-based formats used for representing IFC models. With a broad set of tools for authoring, parsing, and editing IFC entities, *IfcOpenShell* supports a streamlined, programmable modelling process that integrates seamlessly with the rest of the toolchain.

The library defines a structured workflow for generating IFC-compliant models from the individual elements recorded in the database. At the core of this pipeline is the *ifc_manager.py* module, which handles the initialisation of the IFC file and populates it with metadata drawn from various relational database tables. The integration of building components is coordinated through an abstract base class (*ifc_element.py*) which provides shared methods and attributes common to all element types.

Four element-specific subclasses (walls, slabs, columns, and beams) extend the abstract class by introducing geometry-specific logic tailored to each element type, while maintaining a consistent geometric framework as outlined in Section 3.3. In the case of slabs, for instance, separate modules distinguish between different typologies, such as hollow-core and solid variants, allowing for more accurate parametric representation within the IFC schema. The internal class structure of the workflow and the relationships between these modules are represented in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Class structure for the IFC workflow.

To accommodate differing levels of data availability and the required degree of modelling detail, the workflow implements two incremental geometric approaches. The first, simplified method relies on a volumetric definition derived from the overall dimensions (length, width, and height) recorded in the Physical properties schema. Where applicable, this is supplemented by a list of voids, allowing for basic prismatic forms with subtractions to be captured efficiently. This approach is particularly suited to elements with regular geometry and limited documentation.

The second, more detailed method builds directly on the parametric Cartesian definitions found in the Core schema. Here, the geometry is reconstructed from ordered point sequences corresponding to each orthographic projection plane (XZ, YZ, and XY). Each vertex includes an optional radius parameter to define arcs or fillets, enabling the generation of curved profiles or softened edges. Figure 18 illustrates how this information is used to represent the geometric form of an element directly from the database entries.

To reconstruct 3D models from the database, the process can be understood as turning each 2D drawing into a volumetric extrusion and then processing them into a single volume. The first step is to check the integrity of the data. This is managed by Shapely within the database workflow. The second step is to extrude these 2D shapes into 3D space. For this, the overall dimensions are computed to extrude each profile in its corresponding normal direction. Specifically, the XZ elevation is extruded in the Y direction, the side elevation in the YZ plane is extruded in the X direction, and the plan drawing is extruded upwards along the Z axis. Once these volumes are created, they are intersected using Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) representation, which is the result of the Boolean intersection of the three views.

Alongside geometry, metadata management is handled through a dedicated submodule that parses the relevant database tables and embeds the information as property sets (*psets*) within the IFC file. This step is crucial for maintaining traceability between the model and its source data. In the context of the ReCreate project, these *psets* encapsulate detailed donor building attributes, including geographic location, manufacturing facility, year of construction, and classification of the element type. Embedding this non-geometric data in a structured, queryable format not only preserves provenance but also enables downstream applications such as reuse assessment, lifecycle tracking, and semantic analysis.

Figure 18. Example of geometry reconstruction from WKT records.

6. Discussion and concluding remarks

The implementation of a structured element database, aligned with ReCreate's taxonomy and IFC workflows, represents a significant step towards making reclaimed precast elements a viable option in contemporary design practice. The digital representation of elements enables early-stage reuse scenarios to be modelled and assessed without requiring manual redrawing or remeasurement.

Several limitations remain. Manual data entry is time-consuming, and some historical documentation is incomplete or inconsistent. Future work will focus on the semi-automated extraction of geometry and reinforcement data from scanned drawings and 3D point clouds. Additional work is also needed to verify structural capacity estimation routines and to improve the fidelity of IFC exports.

Overall, this deliverable demonstrates that a common classification scheme and digital pipeline can support reuse-oriented workflows at scale. The structured element database serves both as a practical tool for designers and as a foundational layer for future reuse platforms.

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Annex A

Additional wall examples

Figure A1. Prinsen Hof A facade element KG03 design.

Figure A2. Prinsenhof A facade elements G07 and G10 with zone allocation.

Annex B

Data collection checklists

Table B1. Pre-collection preparation checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element inventory	Collect an inventory identifying all structural precast elements that were reclaimed from deconstruction.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Floor Plan drawings	Collect all available floor plan drawings from the archives for metadata and taxonomies.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Construction drawings	Cross-sectional designs of elements, including geometrical and reinforcement detailing.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Inspection data	Compile any available on-site inspection information that might be used to update original specifications.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element Photos	Collect any photos taken before or during deconstruction to link to the element in the database.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Collection templates	Prepare all of the data collection spreadsheets needed based on the available element types from the deconstruction project.

Table B2. Data collection process checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Donor building metadata	Fill in the metadata information for the donor building. Each project should be a single record in the spreadsheet.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element metadata	Fill in the metadata information for all elements by element type. Every element within the deconstruction inventory should have one record in the spreadsheet.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Element geometry	Map the geometry for all unique elements using the information in Section 3.3. Start with the global geometry coordinates, then the void coordinates (for walls and slabs), followed by connection details and corbel details (for walls, beams, and columns).
<input type="checkbox"/>	Additional panels	For walls, if additional non-load-bearing layers are kept intact, map the geometry using the same conventions as above in a separate table (sheet), linking the information with the element's product ID.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Longitudinal reinforcement design	Map the longitudinal reinforcement design using the systems developed in Section 3.3.2. Only record each unique design once, linking the Product ID with the Reinforcement ID. Fill in the anchorage details for each layer or zone based on the available drawings and information. Note that all layer coordinates are taken centre-to-centre.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Transverse reinforcement design	Map the transverse reinforcement design using the same reference systems (zones) as the longitudinal design and the systems developed in Section 3.4.

Table B3. Post-collection checklist.

	Item/Action	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check data types	Check that the data types used for each attribute match those specified in Figure 1 and Table 1 to Table 13. Use the definitions in Section 3 if anything is unclear.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check null/not null constraints	Check that no mandatory data has been missed throughout the spreadsheets. Fields left incorrectly empty will stop the data from being stored within the RDBMS. Refer to the relevant tables (Table 1 to Table 13) to view the necessary constraints.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check for required uniqueness	Several IDs must be unique to satisfy the key constraints in the database management system. Check the requirements stipulated throughout Chapter 3 and make sure all taxonomies meet the necessary guidelines.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check running numbers	Often in Excel, when clicking and dragging repeated values through multiple cells, numbers can incrementally increase, leading to errors in the data. Check that no running numbers have been let loose throughout the spreadsheets.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Linked resources	Ensure that all necessary drawings and/or photos are linked alongside the data in the RDBMS and are supplied with appropriate and clear naming.